

A comparative study on didactic lecture and self-directed learning among General Surgery students in a tertiary medical college in Southern India

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Abstract:

Aim: To compare the effectiveness of SDL with traditional DL for a General Surgery topic among Phase-2 Part-3 students at a medical college in Andhra Pradesh, India.

Methods: This prospective comparative study was conducted among 150 phase-2 part-3 medical students during a surgical competency session. Students were randomly divided into SDL and DL groups (75 each). The SDL group independently studied using provided materials, while the DL group attended structured lectures. Knowledge gain was assessed through 20 MCQs, each carrying one mark, immediately post-session and after one month.

Results: The SDL group achieved a higher immediate mean score (14.5 ± 1.9) than the DL group (13.06 ± 1.6), with a mean difference of 1.44 (95% CI: 0.85–2.03; $p < 0.001$). After one month, scores decreased for both SDL (13.14 ± 2.1) and DL (11.48 ± 2.6) groups, with a mean difference of 1.66 (95% CI: 0.89–2.44). Score reduction was proportionately similar (80% in SDL vs. 78.26% in DL; $p = 0.69$). At the question level, SDL students outperformed DL on 35% of questions initially and 40% after one month.

Conclusion: SDL demonstrated significantly better immediate and long-term learning outcomes compared to DL.

Keywords: Learning Outcomes, Lecture, Medical Education, Self-Directed Learning

Introduction

Medical education is undergoing a paradigm shift to meet the ever-growing complexities of healthcare and the demands of modern-day medical practice. [1,2] Traditional didactic lectures (DL) have long been the cornerstone of medical education, offering structured delivery of vast amounts of information to large groups of students. [3] While DL provides foundational knowledge efficiently, it often lacks opportunities for active engagement, poor attention span, critical thinking, personalized learning, and minimal feedback on their performance. [3–6] These limitations have prompted educators to explore alternative instructional methodologies, such as self-directed learning (SDL). [3]

SDL is a learner-centered approach that empowers students to take responsibility for their educational journey by identifying their learning needs, setting goals, seeking resources, and evaluating their progress. [3,7,8] It is designed to foster active learning, critical thinking, and problem-solving skills, which are essential for medical professionals navigating the complexities of patient care. Furthermore, SDL has been shown to enhance knowledge retention, foster deeper understanding, and improve long-term academic performance compared to conventional teaching methods. [8]

However, the effectiveness of these teaching-learning methods is context-dependent, may vary with educational environments, student demographics, and the specific objectives of the curriculum. While SDL is gaining traction in global medical education, its application in the various medical subjects in the Indian context remains unclear. India's diverse student population and unique healthcare challenges necessitate a tailored evaluation of these pedagogical approaches. With this background, this study aims to compare the effectiveness of SDL with traditional DL among Phase-2 Part-3 students at a medical college in Andhra

Pradesh, India. By assessing the knowledge difference between these methodologies, the findings can offer valuable insights into optimizing teaching strategies to improve learning outcomes in Indian medical education.

Methods

Study Design and Setting: This prospective comparative study was conducted at the Apollo Institute of Medical Sciences and Research (AIMSR), Chittoor, Andhra Pradesh, India. The study focused on evaluating the effectiveness of self-directed learning (SDL) and traditional didactic lectures (DL) among Phase-2 Part-3 medical students during a dedicated session on surgery.

Study Population: The study included all Phase-2 Part-3 medical students who attended the selected class on the study day. Students present in the class on the study day who consented to participate.

Sample Size: A maximum of 150 students participated in the study, divided equally into two groups (75 students per group).

Data Sources and Measurement: Participants were randomly assigned to one of two groups: Didactic Lecture (DL) group and the Self-Directed Learning (SDL) group. The DL group received a traditional lecture on the selected surgical competency, delivered in a structured classroom setting. The SDL group was provided with relevant study materials and resources, including guided facilitation for inter-group discussions, to independently learn the same surgical competency.

Outcome Measure: The primary outcome was the difference in knowledge gain, assessed through a pre-designed set of multiple-choice questions (MCQs). Knowledge scores for both groups were recorded immediately after the teaching session and one month later. Each question was assigned a mark of one for a right answer and a zero was assigned for a wrong answer or an unmarked answer. There was no negative marking. Thus, the maximum score was 20 for each assessment and the minimum was zero.

Statistical consideration: Data were analyzed using descriptive statistics, including mean and standard deviation (SD) for continuous variables. The chi-square test was applied to compare the proportion of the students correctly answered individual questions. Independent t-test was used to compare the average knowledge scores between the two groups. The mean difference was estimated with a 95% confidence interval (CI). A p-value of less than 0.05 was considered statistically significant for all statistical tests.

Ethical Considerations: Prospective ethical clearance was obtained from the Institutional Ethics Committee. Written informed consent was obtained from all students before the study.

Results

We recruited a total number of 150 students in this teaching learning activity. The students were divided equally into two groups- 75 in SDL group and 75 in DL group. Subsequently,

137 students took part in the follow-up assessment, 70 (93.3%) in the SDL group and 67 (89.3%) in the DL group.

Mean difference in score

The total score of the test was 20. While the mean score of the SDL group was 14.5 (SD 1.9), the mean score of the DL group was 13.06 (SD 1.6). The mean difference between the two groups was 1.44 (95% CI: 0.85 to 2.03; $p < 0.001$). After one month, the mean score was reduced for both SDL (mean 13.14, SD 2.1) and DL (11.48, SD 2.6) group with a mean difference of 1.66 (95% CI: 0.89 to 2.44). While 56 (80%) students in the SDL group had a low score at one month compared to the test taken immediately after the teaching, 54 (78.26%) students had a low score in the DL group ($p = 0.69$) (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Distribution of students according to score difference in the tests

Question wise performance

At the question-level, during the immediate post-teaching session, there were seven questions (35%) answered correctly by a significantly higher proportion of students in the SDL group compared to the DL group. On the contrary, the DL group showed a better performance for three questions (15%), and for rest of the 10 questions (50%), the difference was not significant (Figure 2).

After one month of teaching, the pattern was similar- eight questions (40%) answered correctly by a significantly higher proportion of students in the SDL group compared to the DL group. The DL group showed a better performance in two questions (10%) and for the remaining 10 questions (50%), there was no significant statistical difference between the two groups (Figure 3).

Question	DL	SDL	Difference in score	p-value
Q1	21.7	45.7	24	0.003*
Q2	98.6	97.1	-1.5	0.57
Q3	60.9	37.1	-23.8	0.005*
Q4	17.4	27.1	9.7	0.17
Q5	30.4	35.7	5.3	0.51
Q6	23.2	14.3	-8.9	0.18
Q7	76.8	45.7	-31.1	<0.001*
Q8	33.3	64.3	31	<0.001*
Q9	53.6	60	6.4	0.45
Q10	97.1	100	2.9	0.15
Q11	95.7	98.6	2.9	0.30
Q12	65.2	91.4	26.2	<0.001*
Q13	97.1	100	2.9	0.15
Q14	66.7	82.9	16.2	0.03*
Q15	31.9	68.6	36.7	<0.001*
Q16	68.1	92.9	24.8	<0.001*
Q17	98.6	98.6	0	1.00
Q18	97.1	98.6	1.5	0.55
Q19	72.5	97.1	24.6	<0.001*
Q20	100	94.3	-5.7	0.04*

Figure 2: Question wise differences between SDL & DL groups at first test

DL	SDL	Difference in score	p-value
18.5	36.8	18.3	<0.001*
90.2	91.2	1	0.22
68.3	33.2	-35.1	<0.001*
18	26.2	8.2	0.12
35.1	40	4.9	0.34
36.7	34.8	-1.9	0.46
70	44.3	-25.7	<0.001*
25	60.4	35.4	<0.001*
48.2	53.1	4.9	0.17
81.8	93.4	11.6	0.06
75.8	90.2	14.4	0.04*
54.7	86.7	32	<0.001*
67.9	84.4	16.5	0.03*
49	70	21	0.003*
18.7	52.9	34.2	<0.001
55.5	79.9	24.4	<0.001*
92.1	93.4	1.3	0.51
86.4	83.4	-3	0.35
45.7	76.6	30.9	<0.001*
89.9	87.9	-2	0.48

Figure 3: Question wise differences between SDL & DL groups at second test

Discussion

This study compared the effectiveness of self-directed learning (SDL) and traditional didactic lectures (DL) in enhancing knowledge acquisition and retention among Phase-2 Part-3 medical students. The findings reveal that SDL was associated with significantly higher immediate post-teaching test scores compared to DL. This suggests that SDL may provide a more effective framework for immediate knowledge acquisition, likely due to its learner-centered approach, which encourages active engagement and critical thinking. [9]

SDL has demonstrated superiority in knowledge improvement compared to DL in different clinical and non-clinical subjects. [10–12] The knowledge retention is usually more for the advanced learners compared to those who beginners in the medical schools. [12] In our study, both groups exhibited a high knowledge level and a similar decline, but the immediate knowledge level and the retention was more in the SDL. Evidence from meta-analysis suggests that there can be moderate level of knowledge improvement with SDL when compared to traditional lecture method. [12] The SDL method can also improve the skills and attitudes domains when compared to DL method; however, the present study did not assess these domains. [12] Contradictory evidence also suggests that the knowledge improvement in both the methods are equally effective in a surgical subject. [13]

Retention of the knowledge in clinical subjects may depend on many factors including clinical practice in the wards, prior knowledge in the basic and clinical subjects, and subsequent revision of the topic. [14–18] In SDL, the learning is shifted from teacher-centric to student centric approach and thereby establishing an autonomy and self-reliance of the learners. [19] These additional gains among the students might enhance the retention in the long run as we have noticed in our study. SDL also decreases the utilization as it requires only minimal time and human resource from an institutional perspective. Besides, SDL can motivate the learners to become a self-directed learner in long-run. [20]

Despite all the advantages of SDL, it must be understood by the faculty where the students might require a different approach other than SDL and at what should be the approach to reinforce the knowledge. We have noticed that answers to a few questions were consistently better performed by the DL group. The reason could be because of the better explanation received by the learners when the teacher delivered the lecture in classroom. Hence, a customized approach to choose the topic, assessing the readiness of the students, and supplementation with timely supervision could be the minimum strategy to obtain the maximum effectiveness of SDL in clinical subjects. [21]

This study has several limitations. First, the study was limited to a single institution, which may affect the generalizability of the findings. However, the study prospectively followed-up the learners to strengthen the study findings. Second, the study did not account for potential confounders such as students' prior knowledge, learning preferences, and subsequent clinical postings which could have influenced the results. Nevertheless, we assumed that both the groups would have equally affected, and the finding could be attributed to the difference in the teaching-learning method only. Additionally, the reliance on MCQs for assessment, while practical, may not fully capture higher-order cognitive skills or the depth of understanding.

Conclusion

SDL can be considered as a teaching method for the clinical subjects including General Surgery for the medical undergraduates. SDL demonstrated significantly better immediate and long-term learning outcomes compared to DL. While both teaching methods faced challenges in knowledge retention over time, SDL provided a notable advantage in fostering deeper understanding and critical thinking. These findings suggest that incorporating SDL into medical curricula may enhance students' learning experiences and academic performance. However, strategies to address long-term knowledge decay should also be explored to optimize learning outcomes.

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